

FACTORS AFFECTING THE TRANSVERSE STRENGTH
OF GRAPHITE/ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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The most widely used process to make graphite fiber reinforced aluminum involves the chemical vapor deposition of a titanium and boron coating on graphite fibers followed by infiltration of these coated fibers by molten aluminum to form a Gr/Al wire. The titanium and boron coating is applied to promote wetting between the molten Al and graphite fibers. The exact nature and composition of this coating is not fully known. The Gr/Al wires are then consolidated under heat and pressure to form the Gr/Al structures.

One of the major barriers to the acceptance of Graphite/Al as a structural material is its low transverse strength. Despite continued developmental efforts, the transverse strength has only marginally increased, with reported values, as of this time, ranging from about 3 to about 7 ksi. The purpose of this paper is to examine some of the factors affecting this strength in the hope that it will contribute to a further understanding of, and solution to, this problem. The factors discussed include the interfacial bond between the graphite fibers and its coatings, and between the coating and the matrix; thermal expansion variation in composite constituents; the formation of Al_4C_3 , and other compounds at interfaces; and the notch sensitivity of the aluminum matrix.